

investigate the interaction of the sensory endings with dermal cells, as well as to study the mechanisms involved in their peripheral sensitization either by pro-inflammatory and neuropathic drugs. A salient contribution of our study is that sensory neurons from DRGs and TGs can be successfully cultured in MFCs for up to 10 DIV, allowing to investigate nociceptor potentiation and its resolution. Furthermore, we established that axonal endings in these cultures serve as models for studying free nociceptive nerve endings and their modulation by trophic and pro-algesic agents. Our findings reinforce and build upon the existing body of knowledge regarding the viability and functionality of sensory neurons in MFCs, highlighting their relevance as a translational model for investigating peripheral nociceptive mechanisms underlying sensitization and desensitization.^{14,38,39}

Moreover, co-cultures of nerve endings and keratinocytes represent a proof of concept for investigating the interaction and cross-talk of axonal ends with peripheral cells and tissues. We found that keratinocytes modulate axonal function, most likely by releasing growth factors such as NGF that affect axonal excitability.³⁵ Thus, compartmentalized cultures provide a strategy to investigate the contribution of nociceptive endings in peripheral neuropathies that lead to cutaneous and visceral pain. In this regard, our inflammation and neuropathic models demonstrate that the axonal compartment can be sensitized by manipulating the environmental composition mimicking an inflammatory soup or the presence of a chemotherapeutic drug. We found that both conditions increase the activity of the peripheral ends by enhancing the functionality of thermoTRP channels leading to a higher excitability. Thus, the effect of IMs and chemotherapeutic drugs on DRG function can be primarily assigned to a peripheral action. MFC-based cultures also permit to investigate the effect of the milieu composition on the integrity/size of the axonal endings, that is if compounds produce axonal retraction. Not least, MCFs allow also to evaluate axonal transport to and from the periphery,²⁷ and to test the effect of peripherally acting drugs.⁴⁰

Compartmentalized culture methods present numerous advantages, such as being able to expose axons to a different fluid and cellular environment than cell bodies, which is useful for studies of trophic, ionic, and pharmacological regulation. Specifically, in the case of nociceptors, it is of vital importance to separate the soma from the nerve endings because of their peculiar anatomy *in-vivo*. In fact, whereas only the peripheral terminal of the nociceptor will respond to environmental stimuli, both the peripheral and central terminals can be targeted by endogenous molecules.^{5,8} Furthermore, distal axons can be removed performing an axotomy, and subsequently regenerated, which permits many useful approaches to the study of axon growth and regeneration after damage.^{8,14}

These models hold great promise for the future of sensory neurons and pain investigation and open to the possibility of culturing induced sensory neurons (iSNs) derived from

human cells. Using iSNs could reduce the use of animals and avoid problems of unreliability and low translationality of animal experimentation.^{41,42} Culturing these cells in microfluidic chambers would increase the representativity of the model making it more similar to the *in-vivo* morphology of sensory neurons.

Author contributions

S.G. conceived the idea, performed all the experiments, wrote and revised the manuscript; A.L. performed DRGs culture and paclitaxel treatment; L.B. performed DRGs culture; O.G. wrote and revised the manuscript; D.A.A. performed DRG and TG culture and calcium imaging; E.R.C. contributed to samples preparation and took electron microscope pictures; A.F.C. and A.F.M. supervised the project and data, and revised the manuscript. All authors provided critical feedback and helped improve the research's quality.

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Supplemental Material

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